

Conflict management styles of principals in selected campuses of a private educational system

Maria Rona Rhia Escalo Halaman

Abstract

A principal's conflict management strategies are indispensable in the attainment of the school's goals and objectives. Accordingly, this study was conducted to determine the conflict management styles used by principals in selected campuses of a private educational system which were assessed by 129 teacher-respondents using the adapted ROCI-II Form B. Majority of the teacher-respondents are 20-30 years old, college graduates, have rendered less than five (5) years in the institution, and without administrative load. Individual causes of conflicts were the most common conflicts experienced in the system. Regardless of age, educational attainment, or workload, the teacher-respondents' assessment on the principal's conflict management styles showed that the principals often used the different styles with Collaborating as the most used conflict management style. Results of the study showed that there is no significant difference in the assessment of the teacher-respondents on the principals' use of the Competing and Compromising style when grouped according to age. Also, irrespective of workload, the teacher-respondents have the same assessment on the principals' use of the different conflict management styles. However, the responses of the teacher-respondents on the principal's use of conflict management styles vary when grouped according to educational attainment and length of service. Though different conflict management styles were generally assessed as often used by principals, there is still a high frequency of occurrence of individual and managerial causes of conflicts experienced by both teachers and principals. To address this, a program for the enhancement of relevant skills in conflict management to manage conflicts at different levels or situations was submitted as an output of this study.

Keywords: Conflict management; enhancement program; principals.

Maria Rona Rhia Escalo Halaman*

Saint Francis of Assisi College, Las Piñas City, Philippines

E-mail: rhaiescalo2017@gmail.com

***Corresponding author**

To cite this article:

Halaman, M. R. R. E. (2023). Conflict management styles of principals in selected campuses of a private educational system. *SDCA Asia-Pacific Multidisciplinary Research Journal*, 5(2), 1-7.

doi: 10.5281/zenodo.8112117

Introduction

School principals today are challenged with more complex pressures, changes, and aggression; and consequently, countless conflicts with which to cope. Different factors contribute to the conflict. Principals are fortunate to have at their disposal an increasing amount of literature that treats matters of conflict in a meaningful way. In the face of this vast amount of literature, a study made by Msila (2012) asserted that only a few principals are adequately trained to manage conflict. They frequently misunderstand the role of conflict and believe that it should be avoided or stopped promptly.

Kenneth W. Thomas defines conflict as "*the condition in which people's concerns (the things they care about) appear to be incompatible*" (Eklund, 2010). Conflict is an inevitable component of any workplace. However, when it occurs and is not handled effectively, there is a propensity for morale to suffer, absenteeism to rise, and productivity to fall. According to OU Human Resources (2023), managers spend at least 25% of their time managing workplace disagreements, resulting in lower office performance.

The interactionist school of thinking on conflict claims that conflict may be both productive and harmful since it stimulates self-criticism, innovation, and essential transformation (Robbins & Judge, 2018). A conflict had been perceived to be bad and negative, and thus should be disregarded or eliminated. However, a disagreement can be useful if it is leveraged to effect change or innovation. Conflict can strengthen an organization's decision-making and employee relations. While conflict serves to be beneficial, it still wastes the organization's resources and energy. One of the most important skills for managers is to have conflict management. The goal of conflict management, according to Rahim (2023), is to improve group learning and results, including efficiency and productivity in a workplace environment. The crucial factor in handling conflict is not so much the disagreement itself as it is how it is managed.

The number of conflicts in the nation's public schools has increased recently, according to Cerado (2013). This is primarily because of unresolved disagreements among students, instructors, and school administrators. These have had a negative impact on the school's and pupils' academic achievement (Manila, 2016 as cited in Imperial & Madrigal, 2021). Thus, school administrators' understanding of conflict resolution is seen to improve learning, thereby enhancing students' academic performance. Furthermore, Edet et al. (2017) argued that characteristics such as the principal's leadership styles, change management methods, and conflict resolution strategies may be possible sources of conflict and may have a major impact on teachers' job effectiveness. This implies that principals must have the necessary abilities and approaches to handle conflicts in order to achieve the goals and objectives of the educational curriculum in schools.

According to the preceding, the school as a social institution has its own norms and values, and it is distinguished by complex connections among its members: principals, teachers, non-teaching staff, students, parents, and other stakeholders. Conflicts do emerge among members of the school system due to the high degree of interdependence of duties and individual variances in job expectations and would be resolved through the different conflict management approaches (Kalagbor & Nnokam, 2015 as cited in Shanka & Thuo, 2017). The researcher decided to perform this investigation based on these premises.

Conflict resolution tactics employed by a principal are critical to the achievement of the school's goals and objectives. The performance of teachers and students will suffer if a principal lacks conflict resolution knowledge; on the other hand, if a disagreement is managed constructively, organizational performance will increase (Uchendu et al., 2013). Accordingly, this study aimed to determine the conflict management styles used by principals in selected campuses of a private educational system.

The results of this study became a basis for the enhancement of management development programs, specifically, a series of training for the principals to be adept of the different styles of conflict management and develop the relevant skills and to manage conflicts at different levels or situations with a view of carrying out the school's vision, mission, goals, and objectives and to provide guidance on how administrators should manage conflicts, especially in their respective schools.

This study was grounded on Rahim's five styles of conflict management (Kassim et al., 2018), a two-dimensional framework. The first dimension of a disagreement is the extent to which one party addresses his or her own problems; the second is the extent to which one party addresses the problems of the other. Combining these two variables yields five conflict resolution styles: integrating, obliging, dominating, avoiding, and compromising. Each of us, according to Singh et al. (2022), is capable of using all five conflict management approaches. There is no such thing as a singular style of coping with conflict. However, due to temperament or practice, some people use specific models more effectively than others and, as a consequence, rely on them more frequently than others.

Figure 1. Model Concept of the Moderating Role of Work Mattering Between Job Satisfaction and Life Satisfaction

Figure 1 represents the model concept of the study which shows the two types of conflict: the functional and dysfunctional conflict. Functional conflicts are also constructive conflicts that can be channeled into discovering positive solutions that meet people's needs, as well as motivating teams to look at a problem that might otherwise go unnoticed. These confrontations generate fresh ideas for existing problems, as well as greater enthusiasm and renewed energy to solve a specific problem. Dysfunctional conflicts are negative disputes that do not contribute to team cohesion and trust; do not move toward consensus solutions; diminish efficiency; produce unpleasant feelings between parties; cause disruption; and divert team energy to a disadvantageous path. The figure further shows that conflicts are essential; it is the management that sets the difference—if managed well, the result is functional conflict. If mismanaged, the consequences are dysfunctional conflict. Also, it is through intensified series of training that conflict management skills can be enhanced.

Methods

Research Design

This study is a quantitative type of research that used descriptive design since the researcher described the conflict management style of the school principals of a private educational system. Amorado et al. (2017) defined descriptive research as a study that describes what exists and may help to uncover new facts and meaning.

Participants

The respondents of the study were 129 Preschool to Senior High School teachers from the big campuses of Saint Francis of Assisi College (Bacoor, Las Piñas, Taguig). Majority (80 or 62.02%) of the teacher-respondents belong to the 20-30 age group; 21 (26.28%) belong to 41-50; 15 (11.62%) belong to 51-60; 13 (10.08%) belong to the 31-40 age group. In terms of highest educational attainment, the majority (105 or 81.40%) of the teacher respondents are college graduates; 19 (14.73%) are with Master's Units; 4 (3.10%) are Master's Graduate, and 1 (0.77%) has Doctorate Units. Further, in terms of length of service, majority (86 or 66.67%) of the teacher-respondents belong to the 5 years and below bracket; 20 (15.50%) rendered 21 or more years serving the institution; 12 (9.30%) rendered 16-20 years; 6 (4.65%) rendered 11-15 years, and 5 (3.88%) rendered 6-10 years serving the institution. There are more teacher-respondents (96 or 74.42%) without administrative load than that of the teacher-respondents (33 or 25.58%) with an administrative load. The three principals of the abovementioned campuses were also surveyed and interviewed on the conflicts they encounter in school and on the conflict management styles they use in resolving conflicts.

Instrumentation

The researcher adapted the Rahim Organizational Conflict Inventory II (ROCI-II Form B) of Dr. Azfal Rahim. The researcher modified the questionnaire by adding a checklist to it and transforming it into three parts. The first part is the (I) Checklist which contains the profile of the respondents in terms of age, highest educational attainment, and length of service in school. The second part (II) is another checklist of the different conflicts experienced by the respondents inside the school which will be rated according to its frequency of occurrence which used the following scale:

Table 1. Four-point Likert scale on Rahim Organizational Conflict Inventory II

Option	Description	Statistical Limit
4	Very High	3.50 – 4.00
3	High	2.50 – 3.49
2	Low	1.50 – 2.59
1	Very Low	1.00 – 1.49

A higher score means the more frequent the occurrence. The last part is the (III) 28-item Questionnaire which is designed to measure five independent dimensions of conflict management styles: Collaborating (CB), Accommodating (AC), Competing (CM), Avoiding (AV), and Compromising (CO). The questionnaire was also modified by replacing the (pronoun) word "I" with "He" at the beginning of every item and changing the arbitrary scale used to describe the result with:

Table 2. Four-point Likert scale on Rahim Organizational Conflict Inventory II

Option	Description	Statistical Limit
4	Always (A)	3.50 – 4.00
3	Often (O)	2.50 – 3.49
2	Seldom (Se)	1.50 – 2.59
1	Never (N)	1.00 – 1.49

The styles of handling conflict were measured by 7, 6, 5, 6, and 4 statements respectively, selected based on repeated factor and item analysis. A higher score represents a greater use of a conflict management style.

On the other hand, to know the perspective of the principals regarding their conflict management style, another questionnaire and interview questions were prepared. The questionnaire contained two parts. The first part is the (I) Checklist which contains the profile of the principal in terms of age, highest educational attainment, and length of as a school principal / officer-in-charge (OIC) principal. The second part (II) is the (III) 28-item Questionnaire which is designed to measure five independent dimensions of conflict management styles: Collaborating (CB), Accommodating (AC), Competing (CM), Avoiding (AV), and Compromising (CO). The questionnaire was presented to the thesis adviser for checking and validation.

Data Gathering Procedure

The researcher sought the approval of the SFAC President through the managing director for using the name of the school in the research study and for the distribution of the questionnaire to the selected campuses. Upon approval, the researcher then wrote letters to each campus's principal requesting permission to hand out questionnaires to respondents after one of their general meetings to ensure immediate retrieval of the questionnaires and its confidentiality and to have a short interview with them at their most convenient time. Data gathered were tallied by the researcher using a frequency distribution table. Data tallied were then analyzed, interpreted, and presented with the help of a statistician.

Results and Discussion

Table 3. Assessment on Conflicts Experienced by the Teacher-respondents

No.	Criteria	Mean	Interpretation	Ranking
1	Individual Causes	2.75	High	1
2	Managerial Causes	2.51	High	2
3	Other Causes (depending on the organizational culture)	2.46	Low	3
Overall Mean		2.53	High	

Legend: 3.50-4.00: Very High; 2.50-3.49: High; 1.50-2.49: Low; 1.00-1.49: Very Low

Table 3 shows the assessment of the teacher-respondents on the conflicts experienced by them. Individual causes with a mean of 2.75 the interpretation of "High" ranked number 1. The result was also proven in the study conducted by Sumera-Icutan and Sumera-Sagaoinit (2017) that interpersonal conflicts appeared to be the most prevalent type of conflict. Moreover, the managerial causes with a mean of 2.51 were also interpreted as "High" and ranked second. However, other identified causes of conflict, with a mean of 2.46, were interpreted as "Low" and ranked third. The data also implies that other causes (depending on the organizational culture) of conflict were least important, from the teacher-respondents' point of view, compared to the individual and managerial causes, respectively. Generally, the overall assessment of the teacher-respondents on conflicts experienced by them is "High" based on the overall mean of 2.53 and, while workplace conflict is inescapable, it is thought to be beneficial in the building of high-performing organizations (McNamara, 2010).

Table 4. Overall Assessment of the Teacher-respondents on the Conflict Management Styles Used by Principals

No.	Conflict Management Styles	Mean	Interpretation	Ranking
1	Collaborating	3.12	Often	1
2	Accommodating	2.94	Often	2
3	Competing	2.62	Often	4
4	Avoiding	2.53	Often	5
5	Compromising	2.87	Often	3
Overall Mean		2.82	Often	

Legend: 3.50-4.00: Always; 2.50-3.49: Often; 1.50-2.49: Seldom; 1.00-1.49: Never

Table 2 presents the assessment of the teacher-respondents on the conflict management styles used by principals. Collaboration received the highest mean of 3.12 and the interpretation of "Frequently." This indicates that principals should involve and collaborate with their subordinates in dealing with issues in their schools. Being ranked one suggests that Collaborating is the most commonly employed conflict management approach among the principals. In their study, Manila (2016) discovered that most administrators regarded integrating as one of the most substantial and highly desirable strategies in conflict management. Furthermore, the result agrees with the answers of the principals. Their responses under Collaborating got an overall mean of 4.00 with a verbal interpretation of "Always." Other than that, when asked: "How often do you use the collaborating style?" the principals answered "Always."

This was followed by Accommodating with a mean of 2.83. This demonstrates that while dealing with problems, principals frequently aim to meet the expectations of their instructors, giving in to their proposals and viewpoints. This technique, according to Friedman et al. (2000), provides a simple way to resolve conflicts. One party just gives in to the other party, reducing friction. Being in rank 2, this also suggests that Accommodating is the second most-used conflict resolution style of the principals. The result agrees with the responses of the principals when their responses under Accommodating got an overall mean of 2.89 and the interpretation of "Often" ranked number 2.

Compromising ranked third with a mean of 2.87 and the interpretation of "Often." This demonstrates that while dealing with problems, the principals frequently choose the middle ground by utilizing give and take circumstances. According to Rahim (2023), the majority of managers used a compromising strategy to address complicated problems and devise successful solutions. Furthermore, the result aligns with the responses of the principals when they assessed Compromising as their third most-used conflict management style with an overall mean of 2.42 and the interpretation of "Seldom."

Competing ranked fourth with a mean of 2.62 and the interpretation of "Often." This demonstrates that, when compared to other conflict management approaches, the dominant style was employed less by school administrators in addressing disagreements in their schools. It is consistent with the findings of Ghaffar et al. (2012) discovered that instructors believed that principals frequently or never used a dominating style in conflict resolution. Furthermore, there may be various reasons why this technique of dispute resolution is not used. According to Somech (2008), dominating the pattern of managing team issues may be a negative kind of resolution, causing team functioning and performance to suffer. The result is in contrast with the responses of the principals when their responses under Competing got the lowest overall mean of 1.73 and the interpretation of "Seldom." This also suggests that, from the principal's point of view, Competing is their least used style. This further implies that there is a difference in the perception of the teacher-respondents and the principals regarding the principal's use of Competing Style when managing conflict.

Avoiding got the lowest mean of 2.53 and the interpretation of "Often." Though ranked fifth, it was still used by principals often. However, on the responses of the principals, Avoiding got an overall mean of 2.00 and the interpretation of "Seldom." There are various reasons why the avoidance method of conflict resolution is used. Avoiding conflicts is simply a stagnant attitude toward them; it has no effect on solving issues or bringing about changes that might lead to less conflicts (Rahim, 2023). However, there are other situations in which it may be advantageous to avoid conflict, such as when it is of minimal importance or when the potential harm is too significant. Avoidance can sometimes act as a period of calm before a quarrel, giving both sides time to consider their options.

Generally, the teacher-respondents assessed that the principals used the different conflict management styles "Often" with an overall mean of 2.82. Further, the result implies that, from the teacher-respondents' point of view, the principals frequently involve and assist with teachers in resolving issues in their schools.

Table 5. Analysis of Variance (ANOVA) on the Assessment of the Respondents on the Conflict Management Styles Used by the Principals when Grouped According to Age

Area	Source	SS	Df	MS	F	p	Decision
Collaborating	Between Groups	1.29	3	0.43	53.71	<0.05	Reject
	Within Groups	1.19	24	0.01			
	Total	2.48	27				
Accommodating	Between Groups	0.52	3	0.17	26.58	<0.05	Reject
	Within Groups	0.13	20	0.01			
	Total	0.65	23				
Competing	Between Groups	0.95	3	0.32	1.11	>0.05	Fail to Reject
	Within Groups	4.55	16	0.28			
	Total	5.50	19				
Avoiding	Between Groups	5.55	3	0.18	5.76	<0.05	Reject
	Within Groups	0.64	20	0.03			
	Total	6.19	23				
Compromising	Between Groups	0.20	3	0.07	2.85	>0.05	Fail to Reject
	Within Groups	0.27	12	0.02			
	Total	0.47	15				

Table 3 shows the results of the Analysis of Variance (ANOVA) test which measured if there are significant differences in the assessment of the respondents on the conflict management styles used by the principals when grouped according to age. Results show that there are no significant differences on the assessment of the teacher-respondents on the principals' use of Competing Style ($F(3,16)=1.11 < cv=3.24$); and Compromising Style ($F(3,12) < cv=3.49$) when grouped according to age. Therefore, the null hypothesis failed to reject. This means that, regardless of age, the teacher-respondents have the same assessment on the principal's use of the Competing and Compromising Style of conflict management.

On the other hand, data also reveal that there are significant differences on the assessment of the teacher-respondents on the principals' use of Collaborating Style ($F(3,24)=53.71 > cv=3.01$); Accommodating Style ($F(3,20)=26.58 > cv=3.10$); and Avoiding Style ($F(3,20)=5.76 > cv=3.10$) when grouped according to age. Therefore, the null hypothesis is rejected. This means that the responses of the teacher-respondents on the principal's use of Collaborating, Accommodating, and Avoiding styles vary when grouped according to age. This further means that the principals used collaborating, accommodating and avoiding styles on different levels when managing conflicts of the different age groups.

Table 4 shows the results of the Analysis of Variance (ANOVA) test which measured if there are significant differences in the assessment of the respondents on the conflict management styles used by the principals when grouped according to highest educational attainment. Results show that there are no significant differences on the assessment of the teacher-respondents on the principals' use of Compromising Style ($F(3,12)=0.49 < cv=3.49$) when grouped according to highest educational attainment. Therefore, the null hypothesis failed to reject.

This means that, regardless of the highest educational attainment, the teacher-respondents have the same assessment on the principal's use of the Compromising Style of conflict management. Data also reveal that there are significant differences on the assessment of the teacher-respondents on the principals' use of Collaborating Style ($F(3,34)=5.40 > cv=3.01$); Accommodating Style ($F(3,20)=15.57 > cv=3.10$); Competing Style ($F(3,16)=4.55 > cv=3.24$); and, Avoiding Style ($F(3,20)=4.65 > cv=3.10$) when grouped according to highest educational attainment. Therefore, the null hypothesis is rejected. This means that the responses of the teacher-respondents on the principal's use of Collaborating, Accommodating, Competing, and Avoiding styles vary when grouped according to the highest educational attainment.

Table 6. Analysis of Variance (ANOVA) on the Assessment of the Respondents on the Conflict Management Styles Used by the Principals when Grouped According to Highest Educational Attainment

Area	Source	SS	Df	MS	F	p	Decision
Collaborating	Between Groups	0.22	3	0.07	5.40	<0.05	Reject
	Within Groups	0.33	24	0.01			
	Total	0.55	27				
Accommodating	Between Groups	0.83	3	0.28	15.57	<0.05	Reject
	Within Groups	0.36	20	0.02			
	Total	1.19	23				
Competing	Between Groups	2.89	3	0.96	4.55	<0.05	Reject
	Within Groups	3.38	16	0.21			
	Total	6.27	19				
Avoiding	Between Groups	0.79	3	0.26	4.65	<0.05	Reject
	Within Groups	1.13	20	0.06			
	Total	1.92	23				
Compromising	Between Groups	0.11	3	0.04	0.49	>0.05	Fail to Reject
	Within Groups	0.87	12	0.07			
	Total	0.98	15				

Table 7 shows the results of the Analysis of Variance (ANOVA) test which measured if there are significant differences in the assessment of the respondents on the conflict management styles used by the principals when grouped according to the length of service. Results show that there are significant differences on the assessment of the teacher-respondents on the principals' use of Collaborating Style ($F(4,31)=35.46 > cv=2.69$); Accommodating Style ($F(4,26)=22.34 > cv=2.74$); Competing Style ($F(4,21)=11.28 > cv=2.84$); Avoiding Style ($F(4,26)=6.76 > cv=2.74$); and Compromising Style ($F(4,16)=12.02 > cv=3.00$) when grouped according to the length of service. Therefore, the null hypothesis is rejected. This means that the responses of the teacher-respondents on the principal's use of Collaborating, Accommodating, Competing, Avoiding, and Compromising styles vary when grouped according to the length of service.

Table 7. Analysis of Variance (ANOVA) on the Assessment of the Respondents on the Conflict Management Styles Used by the Principals when Grouped According to Length of Service in the School

Area	Source	SS	Df	MS	F	p	Decision
Collaborating	Between Groups	2.06	3	0.52	35.46	<0.05	Reject
	Within Groups	0.45	24	0.01			
	Total	2.51	27				
Accommodating	Between Groups	0.77	3	0.19	22.34	<0.05	Reject
	Within Groups	0.22	20	0.01			
	Total	0.99	23				
Competing	Between Groups	1.86	3	0.47	11.28	<0.05	Reject
	Within Groups	0.87	16	0.04			
	Total	2.73	19				
Avoiding	Between Groups	1.15	3	0.29	6.76	<0.05	Reject
	Within Groups	1.11	20	0.04			
	Total	2.26	23				
Compromising	Between Groups	1.27	3	0.32	12.02	<0.05	Reject
	Within Groups	0.42	12	0.03			
	Total	1.69	15				

Table 8. Independent Samples Test on the Assessment of the Respondents on the Conflict Management Styles Used by the Principals when Grouped According to Workload

Area	Source	Mean	SS	t	df	cv	Decision
Collaborating	W/o admin work	3.12	0.01	0.06	12	0.695	Fail to Reject
	W/ admin work	2.10	0.05				
Accommodating	W/o admin work	2.96	0.02	0.22	10	0.700	Fail to Reject
	W/ admin work	2.91	0.06				
Competing	W/o admin work	2.62	0.05	0.07	8	0.706	Fail to Reject
	W/ admin work	2.61	0.14				
Avoiding	W/o admin work	2.51	0.07	-0.42	10	0.700	Fail to Reject
	W/ admin work	2.61	0.15				
Compromising	W/o admin work	2.89	0.03	0.26	6	0.718	Fail to Reject
	W/ admin work	2.83	0.06				

Shown in Table 8 is the result of the independent sample test (independent t-test) which measured if there are significant differences in the assessment of the teacher-respondents on the conflict management styles used by the principals when grouped according to workload. Results show that there are no significant differences on the assessment of the teacher-respondents on the principals' use of Collaborating ($t=0.06 < cv=0.695$); Accommodating ($t=0.22 < cv=0.700$); Competing ($t=0.07 < cv=0.706$); Avoiding ($t=-0.42 < cv=0.700$); Compromising ($t=0.26 < cv=0.718$). Therefore, the null hypothesis is accepted. This means that irrespective of workload, the teacher-respondents have the same assessment on the principals' use of the Collaborating, Accommodating, Competing, Avoiding, and Compromising styles of conflict management.

Ladeño (2004, as cited in Manila, 2016) found out in their study that most administrators saw integrating as one of the most radical and highly desirable conflict management styles. Furthermore, the result agrees with the answers of the principals. Moreover, based on the result, from the teacher-respondents' point of view, the principals often involve and collaborate with the teachers with or without an administrative load in handling conflicts in their schools.

Conclusions and Recommendations

Though most of the teacher-respondents belong to early adulthood, college graduate; and have only rendered five years and below in the institution, the teacher-respondents still have the maturity to provide a credible assessment on how administrators manage conflicts in their respective schools. Also, almost half of them have rendered more than six or more years in the institution, have gained ample experience, and have gone through various working environments that can enable them to give a good gauge on how school administrators manage conflict in their schools.

The teacher-respondents have identified the individual causes of conflicts to be the most common conflicts they experienced in the school. Likewise, the principals have identified "*Conflicts in decision making and different objectives*," "*Different point of views and miscommunication*," and "*Different age gaps or generation and perceptions*" to be the most common conflicts they experience in school. Moreover, the principals use Collaborating Style when dealing with individual causes of conflicts.

Regardless of age, educational attainment, or workload, the teacher-respondents' assessment on the principal's conflict resolution strategies showed that the principals often used the different styles with Collaborating as the most used conflict management style. Results of the study further showed that there is no significant difference in the assessment of the teacher-respondents on the principals' use of the Competing and Compromising style when grouped according to age. Also, irrespective of workload, the teacher-respondents have the same assessment on the principals' use of the different conflict management styles. However, the responses of the teacher-respondents on the principal's use of conflict resolution strategies vary when grouped according to educational attainment and length of service.

A series of training on the use of conflict management styles and the continuation of professional advancement are needed for principals to be adept at the different conflict management styles and to develop relevant skills in conflict management to manage conflicts at different levels of situations.

Based on the foregoing findings and conclusions of the study, the following recommendations are hereby presented. First, teachers are encouraged to continue their graduate studies in order to update their intellectual qualities. This is one way to address differences in previous experience and knowledge referring to a subject or different perception of the same issue. Further, this could also give them a more comprehensive view or perceptions of the different conflict management and conflict management styles.

It can be also noted that about 40% of the teachers were well-experienced in their teaching career. Considering the above statistics, it is implied that some of the teacher-respondents have somehow gained ample experience and have gone through various conditions and working environments that can able them to give a good gauge on how school administrators manage conflicts in the workplace. Also, they have already gone through situations examining the competence of school managers in handling conflicts.

The principals, based on the result that the individual causes of conflict are high, must investigate the factors that cause conflicts between teacher-teacher or principal-teacher like different previous experiences and knowledge referring to a subject; different perceptions on the same issue; and different objectives, motivations, or interests. This would assist them in determining the true problems and better imagining viable remedies.

The principals, based on the results that the managerial causes of conflict is high, must allocate tasks equally; avoid subjective performance appraisal; and must establish clear and formal procedures, transparency, efficiency, clarity, and addressability to alleviate or prevent conflicts to worsen. The result agrees with Fisher (1990) who stated that the demand for identity, dignity, equity, and participation in decisions that affect them is insatiable for both individuals and groups (as cited in Damte, 2019). Conflicts in schools might result from the organization's failure to meet these basic demands.

It is advised that principals should consider the use of conflict management strategies with high concern for others, particularly cooperating and accommodating, when facing disagreement with their teachers. Most teachers were in their early adulthood, suggesting that they are competent and accountable enough.

Since the school offers scholarships for everyone who wants to continue their professional education, the principals, who are also Masters of Education Major in Educational Management graduates and students, are encouraged to continue their Doctoral Studies so they could gain more knowledge on their field especially on improving their conflict management skills.

The school should implement or conduct a series of training for the principals to be adept at the different conflict management styles; to enhance appropriate skills to manage conflicts at a different level or situation with a view of carrying out the school's vision, mission, goals, and objectives; and, to guide how their junior administrators should manage conflicts, especially in their respective schools.

References

- Amorado, R. V., Boholano, H. B., & Talili, I. N. (2017). *Quantitative research: A practical approach*. Mutya Publishing House, Inc.
- Cerado, E. C. (2016, October 29-31). *Administrator's conflict resolution strategies and school development in Region XII* [Paper presentation]. National Research Conference, Punta Villa, Iloilo City. <https://www.slideshare.net/ErnieCerado/conflict-resolution-strategies-among-school-principals-in-region-xii>

- Damtew, A. (2019). *Cause of conflict between principals and teachers: The case of government secondary schools in Arada Sub-City of Addis Ababa* (Master's thesis, Addis Ababa University). <http://etd.aau.edu.et/bitstream/handle/123456789/19093/Abraham%20Damtew.pdf?isAllowed=y&sequence=1>
- Edet, A. O., Benson, U. R., & Williams, R. E. (2017). Principals' conflict resolution strategies and teachers' job effectiveness in public secondary schools in Akwa Ibom State, Nigeria. *Journal of Educational and Social Research*, 7(2), 153-158. <http://dx.doi.org/10.5901/jesr.2017.v7n2p153>
- Eklund, A. (2010, August 8). *Managing conflict*. Andy Eklund Training for Business, Communications and Creativity. <http://andyeklund.com/managing-conflict/>
- Fisher, R. J. (1990). Needs theory, social identity and an eclectic model of conflict. In J. Burton (Ed.), *Conflict: Human needs theory* (pp. 89-112). Palgrave Macmillan UK. https://doi.org/10.1007/978-1-349-21000-8_5
- Friedman, R. A., Tidd, S. T., Currall, S. C., & Tsai, J. C. (2000). What goes around comes around: The impact of personal conflict style on work conflict and stress. *International Journal of Conflict Management*, 11(1), 32-55. <https://doi.org/10.1108/eb022834>
- Ghaffar, A., Zaman, A., & Naz, A. (2012). A comparative study of conflict management styles of public and private secondary schools' principals. *Bulletin of Education and Research*, 34(2), 59-70. http://pu.edu.pk/images/journal/szic/pdf_files/5_Ghaffar,%20Amir%20%20Naz_v34_no2_2012.pdf
- Imperial, J. G., & Madrigal, D. V. (2021). The experience of conflict management of public secondary school administrators: A phenomenological inquiry. *Technium Social Science Journal*, 20, 24-33. <https://doi.org/10.47577/tssj.v20i1.3530>
- Kalagbor, L. D., & Nnokam, N. C. (2015). Principals' and teachers' use of conflict management strategies on secondary students' conflict resolution in Rivers State-Nigeria. *Journal of Education and Practice*, 6(13), 148-153. <https://files.eric.ed.gov/fulltext/EJ1080516.pdf>
- Kassim, M. A., Manaf, A. H., Abdullah, M. S., Osman, A., & Salahudin, S. N. (2018). Conflict management styles and job satisfaction: A study among Malaysian public universities' academicians. *Asian Journal of Social Sciences & Humanities*, 7(4), 11-21.
- Ladeño, L. G. (2004). *Conflict management strategies of the school administrators and the teaching performance of teachers in vocational secondary schools in Northern Samar* (Unpublished master's thesis, University of Eastern Philippines).
- Manila, B. M. (2016). *Principals' conflict management styles and their schools' performance among public elementary schools in the district of Mariveles, Bataan* (Master's thesis, Polytechnic University of the Philippines-Open University System).
- McNamara, C. (2010). *Field guide to leadership and supervision in business* (2nd ed.). Authenticity Consulting, LLC.
- Msila, V. (2012). Conflict management and school leadership. *Journal of Communication*, 3(1), 25-34.
- Rahim, M. A. (2023). *Managing conflict in organizations* (5th ed.). Routledge.
- Rahim, M. A., Antonioni, D., & Psenicka, C. (2001). A structural equations model of leader power, subordinates' styles of handling conflict, and job performance. *International Journal of Conflict Management*, 12(3), 191-211. <https://doi.org/10.1108/eb022855>
- OU Human Resources. (2023, May 4). *Resolving conflicts at work: Employee information*. The University of Oklahoma. <https://hr.ou.edu/employees/career-development/resolving-conflicts-at-work>
- Robbins, S. P., & Judge, T. A. (2018). *Organizational behavior* (18th ed.). Pearson.
- Shanka, E. B., & Thuo, M. (2017). Conflict management and resolution strategies between teachers and school leaders in primary schools of Wolaita Zone, Ethiopia. *Journal of Education and Practice*, 8(4), 63-74. <https://files.eric.ed.gov/fulltext/EJ1133021.pdf>
- Singh, B., Yarmakeev, I., Pimenova, T., Kaur, B., & Abdrafikova, A. (2022). Comparative study on conflict and its management among teachers and teacher educators in India and Russia. In *INTED2022 Proceedings* (pp. 993-1002). IATED. <https://doi.org/10.21125/inted.2022.0316>
- Somech, A. (2008). Managing conflict in school teams: The impact of task and goal interdependence on conflict management and team effectiveness. *Educational Administration Quarterly*, 44(3), 359-390. <https://doi.org/10.1177/0013161X08318957>
- Sumera-Icutan, S. L., & Sumera-Sagaoinit, C. (2017). Conflicts and resolutions of the school administrators: Basis for innovative administrative program. *Asia Pacific Journal of Contemporary Education and Communication Technology*, 3(1), 252-253. https://apiar.org.au/wp-content/uploads/2017/02/22_APJCECT_Feb_BRR7123_EDU-247-260.pdf
- Uchendu, C. C., Anijaobi-idem, F. N., & Odigwe, F. N. (2013). Conflict management and organizational performance in secondary schools on Cross River State, Nigeria. *Research Journal in Organizational Psychology and Educational Studies*, 2(2), 66-71.